

Overview of Lithuania's Strategic Planning System

This overview of Lithuania's strategic planning system was developed as part of the doctoral dissertation *Government-wide Performance Management in the Context of Complexity: A Collaborative Approach to Performance Management* (Inga Antanaite, Kaunas University of Technology, 2026).

The document provides an overview of the main features of Lithuania's strategic planning system, including general characteristics, the system of strategic planning documents, and institutional responsibilities.

The overview may be useful for researchers and practitioners interested in strategic planning, strategic management, and performance management, providing a general understanding of the structure and operation of Lithuania's strategic planning system.

General Characteristics

The Lithuanian government introduced strategic planning at the central level of government in 2000. The main aim of this initiative was to reduce the gap between governmental commitments and budgetary resources by developing an integrated planning and budgeting system (Nakrošis et al., 2020). During the economic and financial crisis that started in 2008, the Lithuanian government aimed to achieve better results with fewer financial resources by modifying the strategic-planning system, reshaping the management of government priorities, and introducing new instruments of results-based management (Nakrošis et al., 2020).

These are the major reform initiatives in terms of strategic planning and performance management implemented at the central level of government. However, the development of strategic management system is comprehended as a continuous process with a view to respond to existing challenges and remedy negative effects from previous indicatives. For instance, in 2017, the system of strategic planning and budget formulation was improved in order to increase result-orientation and ensure fiscal sustainability. After a review of government spending the Lithuanian government introduced the initiative known as 'change baskets' by earmarking additional financial resources for the implementation of government priorities and other significant legislative commitments. The most recent strategic planning reform was launched in 2021 (Nakrošis et al., 2020). The government declared the aim to diminish the number of existing strategic planning documents, improve their interlinkages, as well as to strengthen interlinkages between strategic planning and budgeting.

In Lithuania, strategic planning is a detailed procedure that defines the overall strategic planning system, stipulates requirements for strategic planning documents, imposes obligations on all budgetary institutions

to draw up strategic plans and budget programmes, to monitor progress in their implementation and to report performance results regularly¹ (Nakrošis et al., 2020). Strategic planning is linked tightly to the budgeting process, integrating all central government expenditure (Nakrošis et al., 2020).

The system of strategic planning documents

The system of strategic planning documents encompasses various types of planning documents from country-wide to individual performance plans (see Table 1). The system of strategic planning documents is determined in the law. However, some types of strategic planning documents are included or excluded with regard to changing social and economic environment, new political will or different approaches towards strategic planning. It could be stated that the system of strategic planning documents is co-evolving in line with launched strategic management reforms.

Table 1. Types of Strategic Planning Documents

Timeframe	Type of planning document					
	Country-wide	Sectorial	Political	Horizontal	Organizational	Individual
Long-term	State Progress Strategy	–	–	–	–	–
Medium-term	National Development Programme	Development programmes (sector strategies)	Government Programme	National Agendas (cross-sectoral strategies)	–	–
Short-term	–	–	Government Programme Implementation Plan Government priorities/ strategic agenda	Inter-institutional action plans	Strategic action plans Annual action plans	Individual performance agreements

Source: Prepared by the Author.

The strategic planning document system consists of long, medium and short-term strategic planning documents (see Table 2). Strategic planning documents are interlinked in a hierarchical manner and builds up a planning hierarchy. All strategic planning documents are directed towards achievement of long-term strategic goals, whereas strategic planning documents standing at the lower level of planning must

¹ The system of strategic planning, as well as the core processes of performance monitoring and reporting, are embedded in the [Law on Strategic Management](#). Requirements for strategic planning, performance measurement, monitoring and reporting are specified in the [Strategic Management Methodology](#) approved by the Government. Note that previously the regulation of strategic planning system, including performance measurement, monitoring and reporting, was a discretion of the Government. There are the pros and cons of different types of strategic planning institutionalization.

contribute to the higher ones. Thus, strategic planning documents are aligned through policy goals and objectives. The schematic presentation of strategic planning system is provided in Annex 1.

Table 2. Main Strategic Planning Documents and their Characteristics

	Type	Brief Description	Duration	Preparation	Adoption
Long-term	State Progress Strategy	Is the main long-term strategic planning document at the government national level, which lays down a vision for the country and development directions. Other planning documents must be aligned with the provisions of the State Progress Strategy.	More than 20 years	Preparation process is coordinated by the Government Office	Approved by the Government, adopted by the Parliament
Medium-term	National Development Plan	Drafted for the implementation of the State Progress Strategy. It lays down strategic goals and objectives. Planning documents standing on the lower level of planning hierarchy must contribute to the achievement of strategic goals and objectives of the National Development Programme.	10 years	Preparation process is coordinated by the Government Office	Approved by the Government
	Development programmes (sector strategies)	Drafted to plan the implementation of the National Development Programme and guide the development of policy sector. It determines progress measures to bring about intended changes.	4 – 6 years	Prepared by line-ministries	Adopted by the Government
	Government Programme	Drafted to plan major reforms/ policy changes and guide the work of the government.	4 years (for the tenure of the Government)	Prepared by the political party(ies) invited to form the Government	Adopted by the Parliament
	Government Programme Implementation Plan	Drafted to plan the implementation of the Government Programme. It lays down government priorities, ministers' strategic actions and actions.	4 years (for the tenure of the Government)	Preparation process is coordinated by the Government Office	Approved by the Government
Short-term	Strategic action plans	Drafted to plan actions to implement development programmes and ongoing activities. Strategic action plans consist of budget programmes.	3 years (rolling)	Prepared by line ministries (and other budgetary institutions)	Approved by ministers (and other budget appropriation managers)
	Annual action plans	Drafted to plan annual activities to implement budget programmes. Action plans guide the work of budgetary institutions.	1 year	Prepared by budgetary institutions	Approved either by ministers or heads of budgetary institutions

Source: Prepared by the Author.

To sum up, Lithuania's strategic planning system could be featured as comprehensive and coherent system whereas long, medium and short-term documents are interlinked through policy objectives and performance results. The political agenda is operationalised through policy planning documents, specifically through Government Programme Implementation Plan and Government Priorities. This makes strategic planning system fairly centralized since major policy changes are planned through the top-down approach at the government level.

Institutional set-up

From the outset of introduction of strategic planning process, efforts have been made to ensure strong coordination of strategic planning process. The Strategic Planning Unit was established in the Office of the Government to maintain the functioning of strategic planning. Along with the mandate to develop the overall strategic planning system, it provides methodological support to line-ministries and other budgetary institutions and performs quality assurance. In overall, the Strategic Planning Unit serves as so-called centre-of-excellence for strategic management. Its core functions are the following:

- Scrutiny of draft strategic planning documents;
- Development of the strategic planning system;
- Strategic planning and policy coordination across government;
- Performance monitoring and reporting;
- Development of guidance;
- Methodological support and capacity building;
- Maintenance of expert network;
- Development of collaboration avenues (Government, 2025).

The Ministry of Finance is responsible for overall performance budgeting and performs important functions relevant for performance management (Government, 2024). It is mandated to carry out spending reviews, coordinate the system of programme evaluation and participate in the preparation for budget negotiations to name a few. In addition, the ministry is responsible for developing and implementing the centralised monitoring information system.

Strategic Planning Units are established in all line ministries. In 2024, in 5 ministries out of 14 strategic planning units were directly subordinated to the respective Minister. In the rest of ministries those units were subordinated to the Chancellor. In general, strategic planning units are responsible for the development of strategic planning documents, monitoring and reporting processes, methodological support to line departments and agencies under the ministry. Among these responsibilities, strategic planning units assess interlinkages between strategic planning documents within the ministerial competence and ensures its coherence, prepare the strategic action plan, as well as the annual action plan of the ministry.

The Government Strategic Analysis Centre (STRATA) serves as an analytical centre, which supports the Government with research-based information to make evidence-based public policy decisions. The main responsibilities of STRATA relate to the following tasks:

- Carry out systemic analysis and evaluation, which is relevant to the Government as a whole. In the annual action plan for 2023 it is envisioned to carry out 9 system-wide analysis/evaluations.
- Provide analytical inputs into the development of Lithuania2050. STRATA has prepared 7 analytical reports as an input into the preparation of Lithuania2050 and produced 4 possible state's development scenarios. It also has organised and facilitated a number of discussions and workshops with society-at-large and various stakeholders.
- Monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of Lithuania2050 and National Development Plan. STRATA should carry out strategic progress assessment towards Lithuania2050 and National Development Plan implementation. In addition, STRATA should provide inputs into the preparation of annual progress report of the implementation of National Development Plan.
- Provide methodological support and hands-on consultations to line ministries regarding high impact RIA (Government, 2019).

In 2022, STRATA carried out 50 analysis/evaluations. 40 percent of analysis/evaluations were initiated and commissioned by the Office of the Government (20 out of 50). Although STRATA has a report template for internal use, structure of the report varies in regard to the type of analysis, whether it is forecast, analysis, evaluation or methodology. However, it is important to note that all reports include recommendations for improvement.

Reports prepared by STRATA are submitted to relevant stakeholders, including the Office of the Government and line ministries, in order to support decision makers with evidence. These reports are not discussed in Government meetings separately. However, ministries indicate in the legislative material for Government meetings if and by what means evidence produced by STRATA is taken into account while preparing the draft decision of the Government. There is a performance indicator in strategic documents guiding the work of STRATA, which measures to what extent insights and recommendations produced by STRATA have been utilized for decision-making.

All things considered, it could be stated that the system of strategic planning could be featured as comprehensive and coherent whereas long, medium and short-term documents build up a planning hierarchy enabling to interlink strategic planning documents through policy objectives and performance indicators. The Strategic Planning Unit within the Office of the Government serves as a centre of excellence for strategic management taking an active role in policy development and coordination, carrying out quality assurance for strategic planning documents, conducting systemic reviews and providing methodological support for budgetary organizations.

References

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